

Newsletter No.6 November 2024

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A research project funded under the EU H2020 programme, developing enzymes for environmental-friendly products

Welcome from the OXIPRO Project Coordinator, Dr. Gro Bjerga

The OXIPRO project has made significant strides in enzyme innovation. As the project is about to pass the second reporting period, we are thrilled to share our latest breakthroughs and collaborations with the wider community.

One of the OXIPRO project's achievements has been its success in upskilling, capacity building, and knowledge sharing across partners. Scientists and researchers are encouraged to work across institutions, sectors, or countries. Read about Lars' experience going to Denmark for fungal expression.

But OXIPRO is also dedicated to sharing our findings broadly, bridging to industry, scientific communities, and the general public.

Key highlights include showcasing Calyxia's and Gecco Biotech's pioneering enzyme encapsulation work, presenting enzyme applications by the University of Barcelona and NORCE and VTT's examination of the sustainability of new eco-friendly sunscreen solutions at fairs, national and international conferences and symposias. Our research has also reached new and young audiences through initiatives like "meet a scientist" events, and our AI-powered podcast series that simplifies complex biotechnological topics.

OXIPRO has less than a year left, but we're more energized than ever to make an impact! Stay tuned as we continue to push the boundaries of enzyme technology.

News Summary

Making Science Simple: Listen to OXIPRO's Innovation Podcasts

The OXIPRO Project is making cutting-edge science easier to understand with **an innovative podcast for everyone**—no scientific or technical background required!

The very first episode, available via the [OXIPRO YouTube Channel](#), introduces listeners to a unique enzyme discovered in a heat-loving bacterium, which could be a game-changer in various industries because of its exceptional strength and stability under high temperatures, where other substances would break down.

Listen [here](#) to the latest podcasts!

[Read about our podcasts...](#)

Exploring Health Innovations - NORCE shows the latest fish protein research

OXIPRO Project Coordinator, NORCE, took advantage of National Science Week in Bergen this year to present OXIPRO's research into the enzymatic hydrolysis of fish protein for the production of nutraceuticals.

The event gave curious spectators of all ages a unique opportunity to try, taste, ask questions, discuss, wonder or be surprised alongside enthusiastic researchers from the research communities.

[Read on...](#)

NORCE

Forskningdagene

Empowering the Next Generation: with Hands-On Industry Experience

One of the OXIPRO project's achievements has been its success in upskilling, capacity building, and knowledge sharing across partners.

Lars Santema, who is currently completing his PhD at the University of Groningen (NL), is spending three months at Novonesis in Copenhagen. Here he talks about how he is benefitting from his time in Denmark:

"In these three months, I'll be working on fungal expression of my OXIPRO enzymes together with some protein engineering, under the mentorship of Kirk Schnorr, a Senior Science Manager at Novonesis. We are hoping that one of the OXIPRO enzymes can be expressed in a fungal strain so we can upscale the production. These enzymes have wide applications in different industries such as textile, pharmaceutical, food, and waste treatment.

[Read on...](#)

How do we avoid harsh chemicals when colouring denim? Norwegian pupils are finding out!

For centuries indigo dye has been used to colour textiles. Researchers are trying to find a way to produce it in a way which uses less harmful chemicals than the traditional approach. A possible solution is to produce it with an enzyme.

Tenth graders at the International School of Bergen were happy to experiment with this idea. pharmaceutical, food, and waste treatment.

[Read on...](#)

Encapsulins: Tiny Cages, Big Possibilities” Pioneering Insights Unveiled:

OXIPRO partner and Gecco Biotech Research Scientist, Ognjen Pećanac, recently captivated attendees at the National Biocatalysis Symposium of The Netherlands (BiocatNL) with his groundbreaking presentation, “Encapsulins: Tiny Cages, Big Possibilities” in which he shared his pioneering work on bacterial encapsulins—tiny protein cages capable of encapsulating enzymes to enhance their stability and reusability.

[Read on...](#)

National Biocatalysis Symposium of The Netherlands (BiocatNL)

Calyxia Features at SEPAWA 2024, Berlin

Among the exhibitors at this year's SEPAWA Congress in Berlin was Calyxia, an OXIPRO partner and pioneering company in tailor-made microencapsulation, including enzyme encapsulation. The display was led by key team member Alexandre Brosse.

As part of their mission to develop new solutions for the industry, Calyxia's presence at SEPAWA 2024 aimed to connect with new customers and promote the latest in microencapsulation technologies, while also shining a spotlight on the groundbreaking OXIPRO project

[Read on...](#)

VTT Presents Exciting Innovation in Eco-Friendly Sunscreens at SETAC

Katri Behm from VTT, Finland – a key partner in the OXIPRO project – recently showcased an innovative approach to sustainable sunscreen solutions at the SETAC Europe 26th Life Cycle Assessment Symposium, in Gothenburg, Sweden.

Representing the project, Katri's poster: '*Decreased ecotoxicity impacts of sun care products with laccase-based solutions*' presented a pioneering case study on decreasing ecotoxicity in sun care products.

[Read on...](#)

OXIPRO Showcases Marine Biocatalysts in San Sebastián

Researchers from the OXIPRO.EU project, including members from the University of Barcelona and NORCE Norwegian Research Center, recently participated in the [IV Jornadas Españolas de Biocatálisis](#) held in San Sebastián.

This biennial event, organized by SEBIOT, brings together experts in biocatalysis to discuss recent advances and innovative applications in the field, and disseminate scientific advances in the use of enzymes in chemical applications and also to promote industrial developments.

[Read on...](#)

Students Keen to Take Up Sustainable Enzyme-Based Products

As part of OXIPRO's outreach programme designed to engage the general public and raise awareness of the benefits of our work, team members in Spain and Norway are reaching out to university students and finding out what they think about our enzyme-based biotechnology breakthroughs. At a recent campaign in Spain, the OXIPRO team from LEITAT led by [Aroa Rey Campa](#) shared insights about the project and conducted a survey at the University of Barcelona during the Catalonia Biotech Day. Find out what the survey revealed...

[Read on...](#)

NEW! University of Groningen Publish Latest Discovery

The University of Groningen has just published its research into OPOx, a special enzyme found in *Oscillatoria princeps* bacteria. This enzyme is similar to those usually found in fungi, with a strong structure and a special pathway for substances to enter. What makes OPOx stand out is that it can handle high temperatures, works well with glucose, and has a unique "on-off" switch that depends on pH levels. This switch could make it useful in technology, like in sensors or in making new chemicals.

[Listen to the pod cast here](#) or read the full paper using the link below:

[Read on...](#)

JBC RESEARCH ARTICLE

Identification of a robust bacterial pyranose oxidase that displays an unusual pH dependence

Received for publication, July 16, 2024, and in revised form, September 30, 2024. Published, Papers in Press, October 11, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbc.2024.107865>

Lars L. Santema, Henriëtte J. Rozeboom, Veronica P. Borger, Saniye G. Kaya, and Marco W. Fraaije*
From the Molecular Enzymology, University of Groningen, Groningen, The Netherlands

Reviewed by members of the JBC Editorial Board. Edited by Sarah E. O'Connor

Pyranose oxidases are valuable biocatalysts, yet only a handful of bacterial pyranose oxidases are known. These bacterial enzymes exhibit noteworthy distinctions from their extensively characterized fungal counterparts, encompassing variations in substrate specificity and structural attributes. Herein a bacterial pyranose oxidase from *Oscillatoria princeps* (OPOx) was biochemically characterized in detail. In contrast to the fungal pyranose oxidases, OPOx could be well expressed in *Escherichia coli* as soluble, fully flavinylated, and active oxidase. It was found to be highly thermostable (melting temperature >90 °C) and showed activity on glucose, exhibiting an exceptionally low K_m value (48 μ M). Elucidation of its crystal structure revealed similarities with fungal pyranose oxidases, such as being a tetramer with a large central void leading to a narrow substrate access tunnel. In the active site, the FAD cofactor is covalently bound to a histidine. OPOx displays a relatively narrow pH optimum for activity with a sharp decline at relatively basic pH values which is accompanied by a drastic

molecular oxygen resulting in the production of hydrogen peroxide (3). Being merely dependent on dioxygen for activity, a large number of GMC-type oxidases have found applications across diverse industries (4–8).

Perhaps the most extensively explored GMC-type oxidases are those acting on glucose and other saccharides. Glucose oxidase from *Aspergillus niger* (AnGOx) is the most studied and used carbohydrate oxidase and can be found in numerous applications (9). It efficiently oxidizes D-glucose at the C1 position to form gluconic acid. Another well-studied but less employed class of GMC-type monosaccharide oxidases is the class of pyranose oxidases (POx) which typically oxidize monosaccharides at the C2 position. Based on sequence similarity and the glucose-2 oxidase activity, POxs have been grouped as members of CAZY Auxiliary Activity Family 3, subfamily 4 (AA3.4) (10). POxs are typically found in wood-degrading fungal species (11). They are thought to fuel lignin degradation by the production of hydrogen peroxide that is

Opportunities

New Job Openings at GECCO-BIOTECH

Gecco-Biotech have two job openings. The first is for a [Technician or Research Scientist - Biocatalysis](#); and the second is for a [Senior Scientist or Research Scientist - Biocatalysis & Process Upscaling](#)

This is a great opportunity to work with a cutting-edge technology provider specializing in enzyme discovery, development, and process optimization.

[More info...](#)

What do YOU think?

In one of the stories above, we talked about how our team from LEITAT engaged university students to find out their views.

This is important for ALL new innovations - researchers and industry need to find out if it meets the needs of consumers and what end-users' expectations and preferences are. And we are all end-users.

So please [take just TWO minutes of your time](#) to complete our short survey by following the link below or use the QR code.

[The Survey..](#)

https://bit.ly/oxipro_survey_1

European Innovation Council (EIC) Releases 2025 Work Programme.

October 29th 2024 the European Commission published the new work programme. Key features of this program include:

- First up, we have the STEP Scale-up Scheme, with €300 million in total for equity investment in companies that are driving strategic technologies. This is designed to help these companies secure larger private co-investments.
- Then, there's the EIC Pathfinder, which has a total of €262 million earmarked for early-stage, multi-disciplinary research that could lead to major technology breakthroughs. Within this, there's €120 million set aside for "EIC Challenges" funding, which focuses on emerging tech like autonomous construction robots and climate-resilient crops.
- The EIC Accelerator brings €634 million to the table for start-ups and SMEs looking to commercialize and scale their innovations, with investments of up to €10 million. Of this, €250 million is dedicated to early-stage companies in sectors such as AI and future mobility.
- Finally, the EIC Transition aims to turn research results into real innovation opportunities, with €98 million in funding.

Upcoming info days and webinars:

You can read more about the program and download the work programme document here:

[EIC 2025 work programme - European Commission](#)

All potential applicants can join the EIC information days that will take place on Tuesday, 5th November: [General Info day EIC WP2025](#)

A dedicated info day on EIC Accelerator 2025 Challenges on Wednesday, 6th November: [Info day -EIC Accelerator Challenges](#)

There will also be a separate information day earlier next year for the EIC Pathfinder Challenges, with the date to be decided, most likely co-organised together with the EIC submit 2025.

News from our sister projects

[New Outreach Materials from our Sister Project - RADICALZ](#)

OXIPRO is delighted to share the latest outreach materials from our sister project RADICALZ. These include a **comic book** designed for **children aged 8 to 12** that explains broadly what enzymes are and how they can benefit our planet.

The comic is [freely available online](#) in English, Spanish, German, Croatian and Catalan (soon to be translated into more European languages)

The project team have also created a **digital escape room for teenagers aged 12 to 16**. It offers a hands-on, interactive learning experience of **45 minutes** that challenges participants to solve puzzles while learning about enzyme-driven solutions to environmental problems.

[Read the Comic...](#)

Enzyme Cluster News - The 10th Issue of Active Site is available now

We are excited to announce the release of the 10th issue of “The Active Site” newsletter, now available [here!](#) This edition is packed with exciting updates, ground-breaking research, and insightful articles that highlight the latest advancements in enzyme technology and their transformative impact across various industries.

[Read Active Site #10 here](#)
[Subscribe to The Active Site](#)

Our sister projects are:

- [EnXylaScope](#)
- [FuturEnzyme](#)
- [Radicalz](#)

And finally...

We hope you've found this issue of OXIPRO'S news of interest.

[Check out our news page](#)

[Read back issues of our newsletter and more of our output](#)

And please [register via our website](#) to stay up to date with our developments and events.

We hold stakeholder consultations with representatives from different fields who assist us in filling knowledge gaps and identifying requirements. If you want to know how we engage those interested in OXIPRO, we've taken a “scientific approach” and [published our guide](#) on how to develop a stakeholder engagement plan.

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About OXIPRO

OXIPRO is a four-year initiative funded under the EU's Horizon 2020 programme and brings together a multidisciplinary team of researchers and stakeholders from 15 entities across Europe to focus on the

development of novel enzymes for environment-friendly consumer products.

The OXIPRO partners are developing and deploying an efficient oxidoreductase foundry using cutting-edge bioinformatics and biotechnology, and by broadening the range of industrial oxidoreductases for more sustainable processes, this initiative will ultimately contribute to the transition to environment-friendly products, with detergents, textiles, sunscreens, and nutraceuticals.

Through the integration of computational workflows and state-of-the-art biotechnological technologies, OXIPRO will expedite the lab to market journey, while shortcutting downstream implementation and ensuring market uptake. This will be supported by ecosystem intelligence generated throughout the project as well as engagement with research, policy, societal and industrial actors in co-creation and interactions to maximise output and enable faster and systemic innovations.

For more information, contact:

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To join the OXIPRO Community and receive project updates, [please register here](#)

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000607.

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